

Full data of the article

Title: *The role of interleukin-10 in mitigating endoplasmic reticulum stress in aged mice through exercise*

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Additional info: -

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Figure 2: Performance Evaluation

Young (Y) Old Sedentary (OS) Old Trained (OT)

Figure 2: Performance Evaluation

Incremental Load Test		
Y	OS	OT
24.3	15.5	18.9
24.2	15.5	15.5
24.6	18.5	21.5
24.6	16.6	14.1
23.2	16.9	16.4

(values in m/min)

Normality Test			
Shapiro-Wilk test	Y	OS	OT
W	0.7943	0.8885	0.955
P value	0.0727	0.3494	0.7727
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	25.16
P value	<0.0001
P value summary	****
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes
R square	0.8075

Post-hoc Test					
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff	95,00% CI of diff	Signific.?	Summary	P Value
Y vs. OS	7.58	4.294 to 10.87	Yes	***	0.0001
Y vs. OT	6.9	3.614 to 10.19	Yes	***	0.0002
OS vs. OT	-0.68	-3.966 to 2.606	No	ns	>0.9999

Figure 2: Performance Evaluation

B)

- Young (Y)
- Old Sedentary (OS)
- Old Trained (OT)

Rotarod Test		
Y	OS	OT
198.3	118.7	239.7
285.7	196.0	212.0
158.3	56.7	186.0
142.0	248.3	102.3
279.7	214.0	163.3

(values in seconds)

Normality Test			
Shapiro-Wilk test	Y	OS	OT
W	0.8664	0.9357	0.9713
P value	0.252	0.6357	0.8833
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	0.631
P value	0.5488
P value summary	Ns
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	No
R square	0.09516

Post-hoc Test					
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff	95,00% CI of diff	Signific.?	Summary	P Value
Y vs. OS	46.07	-70.84 to 163.0	No	ns	0.8847
Y vs. OT	32.13	-84.77 to 149.0	No	ns	>0.9999
OS vs. OT	-13.93	-130.8 to 103.0	No	ns	>0.9999

Figure 2: Performance Evaluation

C)

- Young (Y)
- Old Sedentary (OS)
- Old Trained (OT)

Grip Force Test		
Y	OS	OT
557.5	152.5	275.0
330.0	165.0	290.0
392.5	192.5	280.0
407.5	246.7	357.5
180.0	303.3	340.0

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.973	0.9182	0.8474
P value	0.8939	0.5182	0.1863
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	4.125
P value	0.0433
P value summary	*
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes
R square	0.4074

Post-hoc Test					
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff	95,00% CI of diff	Signific.?	Summary	P Value
Y vs. OS	161.5	4.228 to 318.8	Yes	*	0.0435
Y vs. OT	65	-92.27 to 222.3	No	ns	0.8191
OS vs. OT	-96.5	-253.8 to 60.77	No	ns	0.3415

Figure 2: Performance Evaluation

D)

Mice Weight	
OS	OT
31.2	30.3
34.0	32.7
31.3	31.5
32.0	32.6
31.3	28.9

Values in grams

Maximum Repetition	
OS	OT
15.6	24.2
13.6	26.2
22.4	34.6
16.0	26.1
12.5	25.9

Values in grams

Maximum Repetition	
OS	OT
50%	80%
40%	80%
72%	110%
50%	80%
40%	90%

Values in % of body weight

Normality Test		
	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test		
W	0.8254	0.7332
P value	0.1283	0.0207
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	No
P value summary	ns	*

Mann Whitney test	
Mann Whitney test summary	
P value	0.0079
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	**
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	15 , 40
Mann-Whitney U	0

Figure 3: mRNA Levels

Young (Y) Old Sedentary (OS) Old Trained (OT)

Figure 3: mRNA Levels

Atf4		
Y	OS	OT
1.000	0.862	0.800
1.316	0.891	0.989
1.125	1.403	1.294
1.032	0.656	1.013
1.171	0.846	1.485

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.9447	0.825	0.95
P value	0.6996	0.1276	0.7374
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	1.093
P value	0.3665
P value summary	Ns
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	No
R square	0.1541

Post-hoc Test				
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff	95,00% CI of diff	Signific.?	Summary P Value
Y vs. OS	0.1972	-0.2179 to 0.6123	No	ns 0.6341
Y vs. OT	0.0126	-0.4025 to 0.4277	No	ns >0.9999
OS vs. OT	-0.1846	-0.5997 to 0.2305	No	ns 0.7204

Figure 3: mRNA Levels

- Young (Y)
- Old Sedentary (OS)
- Old Trained (OT)

Ddit3		
Y	OS	OT
1.000	0.703	0.546
0.713	0.332	0.703
1.616	0.525	0.850
1.390	0.480	0.571
1.342	0.466	0.529

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.9532	0.95	0.8532
P value	0.7597	0.7373	0.2047
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	13.09
P value	0.001
P value summary	***
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes
R square	0.6856

Post-hoc Test					
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff,	95,00% CI of diff,	Signific.?	Summary	P Value
Y vs. OS	0.711	0.3015 to 1.121	Yes	**	0.0012
Y vs. OT	0.5724	0.1629 to 0.9819	Yes	**	0.0065
OS vs. OT	-0.1386	-0.5481 to 0.2709	No	ns	>0.9999

Figure 3: mRNA Levels

Hspa5		
Y	OS	OT
1.000	0.717	0.438
0.631	0.420	0.657
0.575	0.610	0.741
0.642	0.495	0.505
0.517	0.575	1.490

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.7918	0.9913	0.8026
P value	0.0694	0.9839	0.0851
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	0.6816
P value	0.5244
P value summary	ns
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	No
R square	0.02

Post-hoc Test					
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff	95,00% CI of diff	Signific.?	Summary	P Value
Y vs. OS	0.1096	-0.3737 to 0.5929	No	ns	>0.9999
Y vs. OT	-0.0932	-0.5765 to 0.3901	No	ns	>0.9999
OS vs. OT	-0.2028	-0.6861 to 0.2805	No	ns	0.7985

Figure 4: Protein Levels

Figure 4: Protein Levels

B)

TNF α		
Y	OS	OT
192617	98583	128782
90214	84200	131051
50641	147701	206752
141322	186045	188312
198781	60419	459563

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1168413	1299604	1255233
954323	1538504	1359526
1002761	1345592	1436301
1173598	1096238	1364201
1199122	890945	1508926

TNF α /GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
0.164853	0.075856	0.102596
0.094531	0.054728	0.096394
0.050501	0.109766	0.143947
0.120417	0.169712	0.138038
0.165772	0.067814	0.304562

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.9140	0.8786	0.8462
P value	0.4919	0.3030	0.2140
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	0.5174
P value	0.6099
P value summary	ns
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	No
R square	0.08598

Post-hoc Test						
	Mean Diff,	95,00% CI of diff,	Signific.?	Summary	P Value	
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test						
Y vs. OS	0.2364	-0.5216 to 0.9944	No	ns	>0.9999	
Y vs. OT	-0.01029	-0.8142 to 0.7937	No	ns	>0.9999	
OS vs. OT	-0.2467	-1.051 to 0.5573	No	ns	>0.9999	

Figure 4: Protein Levels

IL-6		
Y	OS	OT
113616.6	98964.00	90781.33
94135.33	99391.00	77787.67
45749.33	99985.67	104269.0
76232.67	113778.6	96749.67
127369.3	69299.33	122935.0

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1684748	1509591	1296858
1585291	1778709	1276015
1298088	1749557	1106535
1436364	1480766	1016835
1227166	1064629	1105285

IL-6/GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
0.067438	0.065557	0.070001
0.059380	0.055878	0.060961
0.035244	0.057149	0.094230
0.053073	0.076838	0.095148
0.103791	0.065092	0.111225

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.9380	0.9056	0.9331
P value	0.6515	0.4416	0.6177
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	2.217
P value	0.1515
P value summary	ns
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	No
R square	0.2698

Post-hoc Test						
	Mean Diff,	95,00% CI of diff,	Signific.?	Summary	P Value	
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test						
Y vs. OS	-0.006348	-0.6882 to 0.6755	No	ns	>0.9999	
Y vs. OT	-0.4506	-1.132 to 0.2313	No	ns	0.2735	
OS vs. OT	-0.4442	-1.126 to 0.2377	No	ns	0.2859	

Figure 4: Protein Levels

IL-10		
Y	OS	OT
920418.3	557477	1134485
708430.7	655471	1201951
527681.3	1025014	1478495
1199397	707842	962403
2669669	531497	1719807

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1460824	1213068	1391210
1041347	1512870	1197657
793178	1551066	1618063
1069213	1571829	1193672
1161201	1473835	1015274

IL-10/GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
0.630068	0.459559	0.815467
0.680302	0.433263	1.003586
0.665275	0.660845	0.913744
1.121757	0.450330	0.806254
2.299060	0.360622	1.693933

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.7354	0.8446	0.7344
P value	0.0217	0.1781	0.0212
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	No	Yes	No
P value summary	*	ns	*

Kruskal-Wallis Test	
Kruskal-Wallis test	
P value	0.0040
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	**
Do the medians vary signif. (P < 0.05)?	Yes
Number of groups	3
Kruskal-Wallis statistic	8.960

Post-hoc Test				
Dunn's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff,	Significant?	Summary	P Value
Y vs. OS	6.400	No	ns	0.0710
Y vs. OT	-1.600	No	ns	>0.9999
OS vs. OT	-8.000	Yes	*	0.0140

Figure 4: Protein Levels

ATF6		
Y	OS	OT
87268.5	109946.3	168699.3
103778.3	132673.6	191158
91875.25	204827.3	161578.9
83920.08	182823.1	181661
113038.1	174141.4	42000

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1448814	1317151	1056193
1056219	1756239	1042602
858907	1974429	1044378
931275	1572842	924010,5
977540	981520	432782

ATF6/GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
0.060234	0.083473	0.159724
0.098255	0.075544	0.183347
0.106968	0.10374	0.154713
0.090113	0.116237	0.196601
0.115635	0.17742	0.097047

E)

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.9241	0.8789	0.9112
P value	0.5567	0.3043	0.4746
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	4.657
P value	0.0319
P value summary	*
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes
R square	0.437

Post-hoc Test						
	Mean Diff, 95,00% CI of diff,		Signific.?	Summary	P Value	
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test						
Y vs. OS	-0.1704	-0.7746 to 0.4338	No	ns	>0.9999	
Y vs. OT	-0.6405	-1.245 to -0.03624	Yes	*	0.0367	
OS vs. OT	-0.47	-1.074 to 0.1342	No	ns	0.1545	

Ponceau

ATF6

GAPDH

Figure 4: Protein Levels

BiP		
Y	OS	OT
63022.67	86429.33	98833.00
67293.83	167297.3	137025.8
52679.50	139558.6	135011.3
52157.67	99430.67	136804.0
83323.17	129901.6	47167.67

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.9508	0.8290	0.9639
P value	0.7428	0.1368	0.8347
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1448814	1317151	1056193
1056219	1756239	1042602
858907	1974429	1044378
931275	1572842	924010.5
977540	981520	432782

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	9.059
P value	0.0040
P value summary	**
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes
R square	0.6016

BiP/GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
0.043500	0.065618	0.093575
0.063712	0.095259	0.131427
0.061333	0.070683	0.129274
0.056007	0.063217	0.148055
0.085238	0.132347	0.108987

Post-hoc Test						
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95,00% CI of diff.	Signif.?	Summary	P Value	
Y vs. OS	-0.2347	-0.6157 to 0.1464	No	ns	0.2663	
Y vs. OT	-0.6031	-0.9841 to -0.2220	Yes	**	0.0031	
OS vs. OT	-0.3684	-0.7494 to 0.01267	No	ns	0.0584	

Figure 4: Protein Levels

G)

CHOP		
Y	OS	OT
1484557	5308305	1545343
371137.2	3521511	1923048
621823.3	5085290	3076040
210195	3747378	3140049
441033.5	3756218	4290239

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1320199	1147078	1075460
1190921	1349449	1152601
1000683	1143463	1266343
1169700	1018051	1293841
1257541	1046238	1144212

CHOP/GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1.124495	4.627675	1.436914
0.311639	2.609592	1.668442
0.621399	4.447272	2.429073
0.1797	3.680934	2.42692
0.350711	3.590213	3.749512

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.8762	0.9294	0.9057
P value	0.2926	0.5922	0.4423
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	25.18
P value	<0.0001
P value summary	****
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes
R square	0.8076

Post-hoc Test					
	Mean Diff,	95,00% CI of diff,	Signif.?	Summary	P Value
Bonferroni's multiple comparisons test					
Y vs. OS	-3.274	-4.558 to -1.989	Yes	****	<0.0001
Y vs. OT	-1.825	-3.109 to -0.5397	Yes	**	0.0058
OS vs. OT	1.449	0.1641 to 2.734	Yes	*	0.0259

Figure 4: Protein Levels

eIF2α		
Y	OS	OT
1364661	1256274	920398.3
1096934	1321310	936102.3
1224976	1339142	625708.3
2552627	720109	571386
1859372	631490.3	776620

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1684748	1509591	1296858
1585291	1778709	1276015
1298088	1749557	1106535
1436364	1480766	1016835
1227166	1064629	1105285

eIF2α/GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
0.810009	0.832195	0.709714
0.691945	0.742848	0.733614
0.943677	0.765418	0.565466
1.777145	0.486308	0.561926
1.515176	0.593155	0.702643

H)

Figure 4: Protein Levels

p-eIF2 α		
Y	OS	OT
244571.0	798367.5	520232.5
95214.0	665150.0	440484.5
115402.5	240965.0	532127.5
18441.5	269312.0	878448.5
127685.0	678448.0	749830.5

GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
1168413	1299604	1255233
954323	1538504	1359526
1002761	1345592	1436301
1173598	1096238	1364201
1199122	890945	1508926

p-eIF2 α /GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT
0.209319	0.614316	0.414451
0.099771	0.432336	0.323999
0.115085	0.179077	0.370485
0.015714	0.245669	0.643929
0.106482	0.761493	0.496930

H)

Figure 4: Protein Levels

eIF2α			p-eIF2α		
Y	OS	OT	Y	OS	OT
1364661	1256274	920398.3	244571.0	798367.5	520232.5
1096934	1321310	936102.3	95214.0	665150.0	440484.5
1224976	1339142	625708.3	115402.5	240965.0	532127.5
2552627	720109	571386	18441.5	269312.0	878448.5
1859372	631490.3	776620	127685.0	678448.0	749830.5

GAPDH			GAPDH		
Y	OS	OT	Y	OS	OT
1684748	1509591	1296858	1168413	1299604	1255233
1585291	1778709	1276015	954323	1538504	1359526
1298088	1749557	1106535	1002761	1345592	1436301
1436364	1480766	1016835	1173598	1096238	1364201
1227166	1064629	1105285	1199122	890945	1508926

eIF2α/GAPDH (phospho)			p-eIF2α/GAPDH (total)		
Y	OS	OT	Y	OS	OT
0.810009	0.832195	0.709714	0.209319	0.614316	0.414451
0.691945	0.742848	0.733614	0.099771	0.432336	0.323999
0.943677	0.765418	0.565466	0.115085	0.179077	0.370485
1.777145	0.486308	0.561926	0.015714	0.245669	0.643929
1.515176	0.593155	0.702643	0.106482	0.761493	0.496930

H)

phospho/total		
Y	OS	OT
0.258416	0.738188	0.583969
0.144190	0.581998	0.441647
0.121954	0.233960	0.655184
0.008842	0.505172	1.145932
0.070277	1.283800	0.707230

Normality Test			
	Y	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test			
W	0.9762	0.9375	0.8824
P value	0.9135	0.6482	0.3201
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns	ns

Ordinary one-way ANOVA	
ANOVA summary	
F	6.997
P value	0.0097
P value summary	**
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes
R square	0.5384

Post-hoc Test					
	Mean Diff	95,00% CI of diff	Significant?	Summary	P Value
Y vs. OS	-0.5479	-1.035 to -0.06065	Yes	*	0.0263
Y vs. OT	-0.5861	-1.073 to -0.09882	Yes	*	0.0176
OS vs. OT	-0.03817	-0.5254 to 0.4491	No	ns	>0.9999

Genotyping of global interleukin-10 knockout mice

Note: Interleukin-10 knockout (IL-10^{-/-}) homozygous mice show a DNA band at approximately 312 base pairs (bp), while wild-type mice (IL-10^{+/+}) show a DNA band at approximately 137 bp.

Lane 1: Ladder

Lanes 2 and 3: No template control

Lane 4: Negative control (wild-type IL-10^{+/+})

Lane 5: Positive control (IL-10^{-/-})

Lanes 6 to 10: IL-10^{-/-} experimental mice

Jackson Laboratory Strain code 002251

(<https://www.jax.org/strain/002251>)

Figure 5: mRNA and Protein Levels (IL-10 KO)

Figure 5: Body Weight

A)

WT

IL-10 KO

<i>Hspa5</i>	
WT	KO
28.28	30
26.61	30
29.73	29
27.67	28
28.75	28

Normality Test		
	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test		
W	0.9983	0.8208
P value	0.9991	0.1185
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns

Unpaired t test	
Unpaired t test summary	
P value	0.2827
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=1.152, df=8

Figure 5: mRNA Levels

B)

<i>Atf4</i>	
WT	KO
1.089	0.413
0.656	0.888
0.975	0.857
0.809	0.803
0.697	0.797

Normality Test		
	OS	OT
Shapiro-Wilk test		
W	0.9305	0.7314
P value	0.5995	0.0198
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	No
P value summary	ns	*

Mann Whitney test	
Mann Whitney test summary	
P value	0.6905
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in WT, KO	30 , 25
Mann-Whitney U	10

Figure 5: mRNA Levels

C)

WT
IL-10 KO

<i>Hspa5</i>	
WT	KO
0.702	0.332
2.004*	0.868
0.724	0.799
0.516	0.908
0.507	0.728

*outlier

Normality Test		
Shapiro-Wilk test	OS	OT
W	0.7931	0.8117
P value	0.0905	0.1005
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns

Unpaired t test	
Unpaired t test summary	
P value	0.3997
P value summary	Ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=0.8967, df=7

Figure 5: mRNA Levels

<i>Ddit3</i>	
WT	KO
1.176	1.457
1.080	0.640
1.355	0.676
0.858	1.203
0.643	0.846

Normality Test		
Shapiro-Wilk test	OS	OT
W	0.9804	0.8948
P value	0.937	0.3816
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns

Unpaired t test	
Unpaired t test summary	
P value	0.7806
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=0.2881, df=8

Figure 5: Protein Levels

ATF6	
WT	KO
385408.3	233637.3
321426.7	336042.7
297600.3	378062.7
276154.3	336290.3
296151.7	349994.7

Normality Test		
	WT	KO
Shapiro-Wilk test	WT	KO
W	0.8898	0.9836
P value	0.3563	0.9529
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns

GAPDH	
WT	KO
9691166	5031077
6331658	5662695
7535680	5759953
5660757	6196593
6688984	9193666

Unpaired t test	
Unpaired t test summary	
P value	0.1668
P value summary	Ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=1.521, df=8

ATF6/GAPDH	
WT	KO
0.039769	0.046439
0.050765	0.059343
0.039492	0.065636
0.048784	0.05427
0.044275	0.038069

Figure 5: Protein Levels

BiP	
WT	KO
356600	891321
337242	1029561
336213	542962
352466	1258855
539227	1042316

Normality Test		
	WT	KO
Shapiro-Wilk test		
W	0.8252	0.838
P value	0.1281	0.1596
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns

GAPDH	
WT	KO
5592189	6116820
4667658	6737756
5596056	7042441
5371664	7355092
5718511	7388861

Unpaired t test	
Unpaired t test summary	
P value	0.0046
P value summary	**
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=3.884, df=8

BiP/GAPDH	
WT	KO
0.063768	0.145716
0.072251	0.152805
0.06008	0.077099
0.065616	0.171154
0.094295	0.141066

Figure 5: Protein Levels

CHOP	
WT	KO
181564.3	362148.8
113765.4	359433.6
166084.4	290635.5
200855.6	280036.5
291479.1	206918

Normality Test		
	WT	KO
Shapiro-Wilk test		
W	0.9801	0.8476
P value	0.9352	0.1869
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns

GAPDH	
WT	KO
1359231	1468820
696663.5	1390786
900751.8	1140682
1186606	1263768
1329827	1165019

Unpaired t test	
Unpaired t test summary	
P value	0.0225
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=2.820, df=8

CHOP/GAPDH	
WT	KO
0.133579	0.246558
0.163300	0.258439
0.184384	0.254791
0.169269	0.221588
0.219186	0.177609

Figure 5: Protein Levels

eIF2 α	
WT	KO
644777.4	521559.6
564674.7	724821
638357.5	866155.7
712267.1	628877.2
706925.7	514531.7

GAPDH	
WT	KO
9691166	5031077
6331658	5662695
7535680	5759953
5660757	6196593
6688984	9193666

eIF2 α /GAPDH	
WT	KO
0.066532	0.103668
0.089183	0.127999
0.084711	0.150375
0.125825	0.101488
0.105685	0.055966

Figure 5: Protein Levels

p-eIF2 α	
WT	KO
42455.47	160639.5
14483.4	369541.7
56056.33	474942.6
24120.13	430790.1
89530.53	514494.7

GAPDH	
WT	KO
6520507	6259270
5289786	6603289
5617468	6644565
5643695	6936735
6207720	6528551

p-eIF2 α /GAPDH	
WT	KO
0.006511	0.025664
0.002738	0.055963
0.009979	0.071478
0.004274	0.062103
0.014422	0.078807

Figure 5: Protein Levels

eIF2α		p-eIF2α		phospo / total	
WT	KO	WT	KO	WT	KO
644777.4	521559.6	42455.47	160639.5	0.097863	0.247563
564674.7	724821	14483.4	369541.7	0.030701	0.437216
638357.5	866155.7	56056.33	474942.6	0.117799	0.475333
712267.1	628877.2	24120.13	430790.1	0.033966	0.611924
706925.7	514531.7	89530.53	514494.7	0.136466	1.408123

GAPDH		GAPDH	
WT	KO	WT	KO
9691166	5031077	6520507	6259270
6331658	5662695	5289786	6603289
7535680	5759953	5617468	6644565
5660757	6196593	5643695	6936735
6688984	9193666	6207720	6528551

eIF2α/GAPDH		p-eIF2α/GAPDH	
WT	KO	WT	KO
0.066532	0.103668	0.006511	0.025664
0.089183	0.127999	0.002738	0.055963
0.084711	0.150375	0.009979	0.071478
0.125825	0.101488	0.004274	0.062103
0.105685	0.055966	0.014422	0.078807

Normality Test		
	WT	KO
Shapiro-Wilk test		
W	0.8692	0.8141
P value	0.263	0.105
Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?	Yes	Yes
P value summary	ns	ns

Unpaired t test	
Unpaired t test summary	
P value	0.026
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=2.725, df=8

Figure 6. Bioinformatic analysis

GSE97084 (Combined exercise)

XBP1	
Pre-training	Post-training
20.53	14.63
25.38	18.48
37.89	21.79
21.94	20.16
20.86	16.7
16.95	16.64
17.77	16.02

IL-10	
Pre-training	Post-training
0.05141	0
0	0
0.07529	0
0.0472	0.04414
0.0552	0.04161
0	0
0.05362	0

HSPA5	
Pre-training	Post-training
49.41	44.51
55.9	35.73
60.81	53.34
44.5	45.66
41.72	35.05
52.71	44.59
39.17	38.35

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test
	Statistics	P value	(alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.8407	0.1008	Yes

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test
	Statistics	P value	(alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.8389	0.0971	Yes

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test
	Statistics	P value	(alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.8874	0.2616	Yes

Paired t test	
P value	0.0399
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=2.614, df=6
Number of pairs	7

Paired t test	
P value	0.0543
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=2.387, df=6
Number of pairs	7

Paired t test	
P value	0.0416
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=2.583, df=6
Number of pairs	7

GSE97084 (Combined exercise)

IL-6	
Pre-training	Post-training
0.05475	0.06591
0	0
0.1604	0
0	0
0.02939	0.04432
0	0.05127
0.02856	0

TNF-A	
Pre-training	Post-training
0.04994	0.06012
0	0
0.1463	0.06421
0.1375	0.08576
0.2145	0.3234
0.4837	0.09353
0.1563	0.2267

ATF4	
Pre-training	Post-training
55.47	51.41
62.68	55.85
62.74	53.9
73.37	67.24
56.84	59.81
73.21	66
63.67	56.79

Normality of Residuals			
		Passed	
		normality	
		test	
		(alpha=	
	Statistics	P value	0,05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7752	0.0231	No

Normality of Residuals			
		Passed	
		normality	
		test	
		(alpha=	
	Statistics	P value	0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.8236	0.0695	Yes

Normality of Residuals			
		Passed	
		normality	
		test	
		(alpha=	
	Statistics	P value	0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7735	0.0222	No

Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test	
P value	>0.9999
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No

Paired t test	
P value	0.4716
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=0.7681, df=6
Number of pairs	7

Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed rank test	
P value	0.0313
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes

GSE97084 (Combined exercise)

ATF6

Pre-training	Post-training
5.055	5.306
6.398	5.22
7.59	6.965
6.474	5.964
6.922	4.977
4.732	4.575
5.55	5.882

Normality of Residuals

	Statistics	P value	Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.9380	0.6204	Yes

Paired t test

P value	0.1234
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=1.792, df=6
Number of pairs	7

DDT13

Pre-training	Post-training
15.86	12.07
13.1	13.54
13.23	20.21
14.43	15.88
19.4	17.1
9.186	13.46
12.91	12.49

Normality of Residuals

	Statistics	P value	Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.9707	0.9038	Yes

Paired t test

P value	0.5249
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=0.6749, df=6
Number of pairs	7

GSE165630 (Aerobic exercise)

DDTI3	
Sedentary	Trained
51.26	19.72
49.25	28.51
41.47	30.78
30.35	25.47
105.4	24.65

ATF6	
Sedentary	Trained
501	3.95
10.47	3.68
4.06	3.27
4.3	3.68
2.79	3.75

ATF4	
Sedentary	Trained
77.81	51.41
117.7	64.97
67.58	52.91
83.4	61.94
90.86	83.57

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7867	0.0100	No

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7585	0.0045	No

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.9144	0.3129	Yes

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.0159
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	39 , 16
Mann-Whitney U	1

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.1349
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	35 , 20
Mann-Whitney U	5

Unpaired t test	
P value	0.0435
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=2.395, df=8

GSE165630 (Aerobic exercise)

HSPA5	
Sedentary	Trained
80.62	34.21
145	91.09
56.95	45.78
48.82	59.42
48.6	56.63

XBP1	
Sedentary	Trained
31.77	15.73
80.19	24.88
30.63	18.77
27.04	21.83
23.28	26.06

IL-6	
Sedentary	Trained
3.722	4.005
2.154	2.329
0.3217	0.000
0.1446	2.943
2.267	2.213

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	Statistics	P value	No
	0.8414	0.0459	

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	Statistics	P value	No
	0.7515	0.0037	

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	Statistics	P value	Yes
	0.9688	0.8794	

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.5476
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	31 , 24
Mann-Whitney U	9

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.0317
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	38 , 17
Mann-Whitney U	2

Unpaired t test	
P value	0.7417
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=0.3413, df=8

GSE165630 (Aerobic exercise)

TNF-A	
Sedentary	Trained
1.132	0.07306
0.5126	0.2125
0	0.3232
0.1055	0.2685
0.4354	0.173

IL-10	
Sedentary	Trained
1.515	0
1.466	0.08749
0.1394	0.1426
0.1629	0.05527
0.1494	0.05938

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	Statistics	P value	No
	0.6250	0.0001	

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	Statistics	P value	Yes
	0.8552	0.0670	

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.5476
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	31 , 24
Mann-Whitney U	9

Unpaired t test	
P value	0.0975
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=1.876, df=8

GSE165630 (Resistance exercise)

DDT13	
Sedentary	Trained
51.26	27.83
49.25	19.65
41.47	19.54
30.35	25.71
105.4	

ATF6	
Sedentary	Trained
5.01	4.56
10.47	4.12
4.06	3.95
4.3	4.34
2.79	

ATF4	
Sedentary	Trained
77.81	82.09
117.7	84.08
67.58	58.21
83.4	64.56
90.86	

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7905	0.0159	No

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7761	0.0109	No

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.9527	0.7200	Yes

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.0159
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	35 , 10
Mann-Whitney U	0

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.9048
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	26 , 19
Mann-Whitney U	9

Unpaired t test	
P value	0.2130
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=1.370, df=7

GSE165630 (Resistance exercise)

HSPA5	
Sedentary	Trained
80.62	47.27
145	33.74
56.95	44.26
48.82	42.34
48.6	

XBP1	
Sedentary	Trained
31.77	20.87
80.19	17.17
30.63	18.82
27.04	19.17
23.28	

IL-6	
Sedentary	Trained
3.722	0.07953
2.154	0.02136
0.3217	0.0524
0.1446	0.05022
2.267	

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7910	0.0161	No

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.7254	0.0028	No

Normality of Residuals			
			Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.8970	0.2354	Yes

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.0159
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	35 , 10
Mann-Whitney U	0

Mann Whitney test	
P value	0.0159
Exact or approximate P value?	Exact
P value summary	*
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
Sum of ranks in column A,B	35 , 10
Mann-Whitney U	0

Unpaired t test	
P value	0.0633
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=2.205, df=7

GSE165630 (Resistance exercise)

TNF-A

Sedentary	Trained
1.132	0.2902
0.5126	0.0779
0	0
0.1055	0.0916
0.4354	

IL-10

Sedentary	Trained
1.515	0.04978
1.466	0.08024
0.1394	0.0492
0.1629	0.04716
0.1494	

Normality of Residuals

Test name	Statistics	P value	Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Anderson-Darling (A2*)	0.4256	0.2431	Yes
D'Agostino-Pearson omnibus (K2)	4.563	0.1021	Yes
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.9098	0.3145	Yes

Normality of Residuals

Test name	Statistics	P value	Passed normality test (alpha=0.05)?
Anderson-Darling (A2*)	0.6508	0.0593	Yes
D'Agostino-Pearson omnibus (K2)	0.9698	0.6158	Yes
Shapiro-Wilk (W)	0.8393	0.0567	Yes

Unpaired t test

P value	0.2071
P value summary	Ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=1.390, df=7

Unpaired t test

P value	0.1345
P value summary	ns
Significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No
One- or two-tailed P value?	Two-tailed
t, df	t=1.692, df=7